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Ecology and Protein Composition of *Polypedates leucomystax* (Gravenhorst, 1829) (Anura: Rhacophoridae) Foam Nests from Peninsular Malaysia

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Author SS designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Authors MNI and SHK managed the analyses of the study. Author NN managed the literature searches. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

The four-lined tree frog, *Polypedates leucomystax*, spawns its eggs in a moist structure called a foam nest. Four foam nests constructed by this species were collected from the Sungai Sedim Recreational Forest, Kedah, Peninsular Malaysia. Two foam nests were found deposited on the leaves of low vegetation hanging over a rock pool. One was attached inside a water tank, and one was found on grass near an ephemeral puddle. In the laboratory, the foam nests were freeze-dried and the protein concentrations quantified, fractionated, and analyzed using LC-MS/MS. Twenty-two

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proteins, including seven enzymes, six structural proteins, five regulatory proteins, three receptors, and one antimicrobial peptide (AMP) were found in the foam nests. The function of the AMP (brevinin-2 type) is believed to protect the frog eggs from pathogenic microorganisms.

Keywords: Amphibian; foam nest; protein and peptide; pharmacological effect; *Polypedates leucomystax*; Peninsular Malaysia.

1. INTRODUCTION

Polypedates leucomystax is a medium to large-sized frog. The snout-vent length (SVL) of males and females reaches 37–50 and 57–75 mm, respectively [1]. This commensal species is widely distributed throughout Bangladesh, Brunei, Cambodia, China, India, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, Nepal, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam [2]. They occupy various habitats and are usually found around human habitations in urban and rural areas [3,4,2]. During the breeding period, the females produce eggs in a white moist structure called a foam nest. The foam nest is created from skin secretions, produced by both the male and female frogs, and wiped by hind limbs onto the posterior dorsum. Usually, this foam nest is deposited on tree branches, twigs, or leaves and hangs over stagnant water bodies such as ephemeral pools and puddles [3,4,1].

Many studies have focused on the bioactive compounds contained in the skin secretions of frogs [5,6,7]. These secretions are believed to contain various chemical substances, which produce a variety of pharmacological effects including antimicrobial activities [8,9]. Two frog species from Peninsular Malaysia, namely *Odorrana hosii* and *Hylarana picturata*, produce a variety of antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) in their skin secretions [10]. Eight AMPs, belonging to the esculentin-1 (1 peptide), esculentin-2 (1 peptide), brevinin-1 (2 peptides), brevinin-2 (2 peptides), and nigrocin-2 (2 peptides) families, were detected in the skin secretions of *O. hosii*. Eight peptides, belonging to the brevinin-1 (2 peptides), brevinin-2 (5 peptides), and temporin (1 peptide) families, were detected in the skin secretions of *H. picturata* [10]. Skin secretions of *Hylarana erythraea*, from Vietnam, contain several AMPs belonging to the brevinin-1 (3 peptides), brevinin-2 (2 peptides), esculentin-2 (4 peptide), and temporin (1 peptide) families [11].

Amphibian foam nests perform various functions including: protection against predators and pathogens [12]; prevention of egg-mass dehydration [13,14]; provision of respiratory

advantages to embryos [15]; gliding substrates for larvae [14]; and provision of nutrients for the development of embryos [16]. The composition of anuran foam nests has been studied by several researchers. Kabisch et al. [14] analyzed the foam nests of *P. leucomystax*, which contained more than 93% protein. The proteins consisted of 17 amino acids; the main proteins were asparagines, lysine, and glutamate. Cooper et al. [17] discovered unusual primary structures and surfactant activity in ranaspumins proteins in the foam nests of *Physalaemus pustulosus*. McMahon et al. [18] described the crystal structure of a 13 kDa surfactant protein, ranasmurfin, which was isolated from the foam nests of *P. leucomystax*. Hissa et al. [16] detected a strong surfactant protein, *Lv-ranaspumin*, in *Leptodactylus vastus*. These findings indicate the variety of chemical substances, especially proteins, contained in amphibian foam nests. Therefore, this study was conducted to analyze the ecology and protein composition of *P. leucomystax* foam nests.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Foam Nest Collection

Four *P. leucomystax* foam nests were collected from the Sungai Sedim Recreational Forest, Kedah, Peninsular Malaysia (5°25'N, 100°46'E; elevation <150 m above sea level). The foam nests were collected by searching around stagnant water bodies such as rock pools and temporary puddles. The foam nests were collected by hand and placed into moist plastic bags. To confirm that the foam nests belonged to the *P. leucomystax* species, each mating pair was collected. Visual examination indicated that the morphology of each mating pair was in accordance with *P. leucomystax* [3].

2.2 Freeze Drying

Eggs were separated from the foam nests using forceps. The foam nests were then placed into 50 mL Falcon tubes and frozen at -35°C. After 24 hours, the frozen foam nests were transferred into a freeze-dry machine (Labconco) and

processed for 24 hours. The optimal temperature and vacuum conditions were -47°C and 0.025 mbar, respectively. Fifteen milligrams of each freeze-dried foam nest was added to 1 mL of 40 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.8) extraction buffer. The mixtures were left for 20 minutes and occasionally stirred. The mixtures were then centrifuged at $12,000 \times g$ for 30 minutes. The supernatants were collected and stored at -35°C .

2.3 Bradford Assay

The total protein concentration of the foam nests was quantified using a Bradford assay [19]. Five micro liters of each supernatant was mixed with 250 μL of Bradford reagent in a 96-well plate and incubated at ambient temperature for 15 minutes. A standard curve ranging from 0–2.0 mg/mL was constructed with absorbance set at 595 nm. The total protein concentration of each sample was determined and averaged by comparing the absorbance value against the standard curve.

2.4 Protein Fractionation

Protein fractionation was conducted using a Gel free 8100 fractionation system (Expedeon, CA, USA). The procedure was carried out according to the protocol of Witkowski and Harkins [20]. Two hundred micrograms of each sample was loaded into a 10% Tris-Acetate cartridge. Twelve fractions were collected and concentrated using a vacuum concentrator.

2.5 Protein Digestion

Protein digestion was carried out according to Kinter and Sherman [21]. The samples were re-suspended in 100 μL of 6 M urea and 10 mg/mL of 100 mM Tris buffer. DTT (200 mM) was added to each sample and the mixture held at room temperature for one hour. Iodoacetamide (200 mM) was then added and incubated at room temperature for a further hour followed by addition of excess DTT to consume unreacted iodoacetamide. The concentration of urea in the samples was then reduced by adding 775 μL of water. For digestion purpose, 20 μg of trypsin solution (Promega, WI, USA) was added to each sample and incubated overnight at 37°C . The digestion was halted the next day by adjusting the pH of the buffer to $\text{pH} < 6$.

2.6 LC-MS/MS Analysis

Each sample was mixed with 100 μL of 0.1% formic acid in de-ionized water and filtered using

a 0.45 μm regenerated cellulose (RC) membrane syringe filter (Sartorius AG, Goettingen, Germany). The analysis was conducted using a LTQ-Orbitrap Velos Pro mass spectrometer, coupled with an Easy-nLC II nano liquid chromatography system. A C18 Easy column (10 cm, 0.75 mm i.d., 3 μm) (Thermo Scientific, San Jose, CA, USA) was used as the analytical column and a C18 Easy column (2 cm, 0.1 mm i.d., 5 μm) (Thermo Scientific, San Jose, CA, USA) was used as the pre-column. The analytical column was equilibrated at a flow rate of 0.3 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 4 μL ; the pre-column was equilibrated at 3 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 15 μL ; and 5 μL of each sample was injected and chromatographically separated at a flow rate of 0.3 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. Running buffers (A) 0.1% formic acid in de-ionized water and (B) 0.1% formic acid in acetonitrile were used. The samples were eluted using a gradient of 5% to 100% of buffer B for 80 minutes. The eluent was sprayed into the mass spectrometer at 2.1 kV (voltage source), and the capillary temperature was set at 220°C . Protein and peptides were detected using full-scan mass analysis from m/z 300–2,000 at a resolving power of 60,000 (at m/z 400, FWHM; 1-s acquisition). Data-dependent MS/MS analyses (ITMS) were triggered by the eight most abundant ions from a parent mass list of predicted peptides, with rejection or unassigned charge states. Collision-induced dissociation (CID) was used as a fragmentation technique with a collision energy of 35. Each sample was analyzed twice.

2.7 Protein and Peptide Identification (*De Novo* Sequencing)

PEAKS Studio Version 7 (Bioinformatics Solution, Waterloo Canada) was used to perform *de novo* sequencing and database matching. The National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) amphibian database (as of October 2014) was used for database matching. Parent mass and precursor mass tolerance were set at 0.1 Da. A false detection rate (FDR) of less than 0.1% and a significant score of $-10\lg P$ for proteins greater than 30 were used for protein acceptance. A minimum unique peptide was set at 1 and a maximum variable post-translational modification was set at 4.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mating pairs (Fig. 1) and foam nests (Fig. 2) of *P. leucomystax* were collected from the Sungai

Sedim Recreational Forest. In Fig. 1, the small-sized frog is male (top) and the larger frog is female (bottom). Two foam nests were found deposited on the leaves of low vegetation approximately 1 m above a rock pool. The rock pool was intermediate-sized, being approximately 4 m in length, 2 m wide, and 5–35 cm deep; contained clear water; had a sandy-gravel bed; and was covered with leaf litter and twigs. It was bordered by low vegetation and was directly exposed to sunlight. Tadpoles of other frog species, *Microhyla heymonsi* and *Fejervarya limnocharis*, were also found living in the pool. A single foam nest was collected from the inner surface of a water tank, which was located near a toilet. The water tank was about 1.5 m long and 1 m wide and was filled with clean tap water. This foam nest was located approximately 22 cm above the water level. The fourth foam nest was found deposited on grass at the edge of an ephemeral puddle. This intermediate-sized puddle was approximately 2 m long, 1 m wide, 2–15 cm deep, and located 6–7 m from a main river. It contained cloudy water, had a silty bottom, and was covered with sediments. The puddle was bordered by small sized grass and exposed to sunlight.

Anuran species lives in different types of environment and reproduce by a variety of modes. To date, 39 types of reproduction modes have been recognized and described in anurans, including the formation of foam nests [22,23]. Various frog species from Malaysia, especially tree frogs such as *Polypedates macrotis*, *P. ottilophus*, *P. leucomystax*, *Rhacophorus nigropalmatus*, and *R. pardalis* deposit their eggs in foam nests during their breeding seasons [24]. Usually, foam nests are located adjacent to stagnant water bodies. Inger [25] found the foam nests of *P. leucomystax* attached to vegetation and rocks at the edges of standing or slowly flowing water. Berry [3] discovered foam nests in tubs around houses, tanks, rainwater butts, or on leaves overhanging small pools of water. Sheridan [26] found foam nests belonging to *P. leucomystax* above water in emergent vegetation or other suitable substrates. It breeds in standing water bodies such as natural ponds, cattle tanks, cisterns, and flowerpots. In this study, the foam nests of *P. leucomystax* were found deposited on leaves hanging over a rock pool, among grass, and attached inside a water tank.

Fig. 1. Male (top) and female (bottom) *P. leucomystax* in amplexus

Fig. 2. The foam nest of *P. leucomystax*

The average total protein concentration of the foam nests in the current study was 1.10 mg/mL. The seven-point calibration curve, ranged from 0–2.0 mg/mL ($y=0.3652x+0.006$; $R^2=0.9914$) (Fig. 3). Twenty-two proteins, including seven enzymes (32%), six structural proteins (27%), five regulatory proteins (23%), three receptors (13%), and one AMP (5%) were detected in the *P. leucomystax* foam nests (Table 1). The enzymes detected in the foam nests were prohormone convertase 1, duodenase-1, Ca^{2+} -ATPase, membrane protease subunit 2, exosome complex exonuclease RRP43, and NADH-ubiquinone oxidoreductase chain 2. The structural proteins were collagen alpha-2(1) chain, alpha 1 type 1 collagen, adult keratin RAK, larval type 1 keratin, and larval specific keratin 1. The regulatory proteins were pumilio-related protein, protein 90B, C10orf27, and tropomyosin-1 alpha chain. The receptors were ryanodine receptor alpha isoform, ryanodine receptor beta isoform, and progesterone receptor. The single AMP belongs to the brevenin-2 family. The

proteins, based on their biological functions, are shown in Fig. 4.

Various chemical substances including proteins, peptides, steroids, and biogenic amines have been detected in the skin secretions of amphibians [27,28]. Previous reports have documented AMPs in the skin secretions of

amphibian species belonging to the families of Pipidae, Hylidae, Hyperoliidae, and Ranidae [29,30,31]. These AMP molecules are 10–50 amino acid residues in length, with remarkably diverse structures [31,32]. From our results, a single AMP belonging to the brevinin-2 family was detected in the foam nest of *P. leucomystax*.

Fig. 3. The seven-point calibration curve (protein concentration of foam nests = 1.10 mg/mL)

Fig. 4. Types of protein detected in *P. leucomystax* foam nests

Table 1. List of proteins detected in *P. leucomystax* foam nests

Accession	Score (%)	-10I gP	Coverage (%)	#Peptides	#Unique	Avg. Mass	Types of protein	Description
sp O42350 CO1A2_LITCT	14.1	74.74	19	11	11	127644	Structural	Collagen alpha-2(I) chain OS=Lithobates catesbeiana GN=COL1A2 PE=2 SV=1
tr O93251 O93251_LITCT	13.2	72.95	26	16	16	137251	Structural	Alpha 1 type I collagen OS=Lithobates catesbeiana GN=alpha 1 type I collagen PE=2 SV=1
tr D8L948 D8L948_RANLE	12.3	40.71	6	3	3	129202	Regulatory	Pumilio-related protein OS=Rana lessonae GN=pum1 PE=2 SV=1
tr Q76FG1 Q76FG1_LITCT	11.4	36.06	10	2	2	82881	Enzyme	Prohormone convertase 1 OS=Lithobates catesbeiana GN=pc1 PE=2 SV=1
tr O93583 O93583_PELRI	10.2	36.06	10	2	2	82966	Enzyme	Prohormone convertase 1 OS=Pelophylax ridibundus PE=2 SV=1
tr C1C3U9 C1C3U9_LITCT	20.6	31.31	7	1	1	28870	Regulatory	Coiled-coil domain-containing protein 90B, mitochondrial OS=Lithobates catesbeiana GN=CC90B PE=2 SV=1
tr C1C450 C1C450_LITCT	5.1	29.97	13	2	2	27687	Enzyme	Duodenase-1 OS=Lithobates catesbeiana GN=DDN1 PE=2 SV=1
sp P0C5X5 B2DYE_RANDY	5.3	27.07	35	1	1	3675	AMP	Brevinin-2DYe OS=Rana dybowskii PE=1 SV=1
tr Q91313 Q91313_LITCT	12.2	25.59	0	1	1	571299	Receptor	Ryanodine receptor alpha isoform OS=Lithobates catesbeiana GN=FROG-ARR PE=2 SV=1
tr Q91319 Q91319_LITCT	12.0	25.59	0	1	1	553055	Receptor	Ryanodine receptor beta isoform OS=Lithobates catesbeiana GN=FROG-BRR PE=2 SV=2
tr Q9DDB8 Q9DDB8_RANSY	12.1	24.62	2	1	1	109266	Enzyme	Ca ²⁺ -ATPase OS=Rana sylvatica GN=atp2A1 PE=2 SV=1

Accession	Score (%)	-10I gP	Coverage (%)	#Peptides	#Unique	Avg. Mass	Types of protein	Description
tr Q910C2 Q910C2_LITCT	10.9	24.44	3	1	1	46595	Structural	Adult keratin RAK (Fragment) OS=Lithobates catesbeiana GN=rak PE=2 SV=1
tr A7TUG6 A7TUG6_LITCT	6.2	24.44	2	1	1	51694	Structural	Larval type I keratin OS=Lithobates catesbeiana GN=RLKI PE=2 SV=1
tr F5BBF0 F5BBF0_RANLU	5.2	24.44	10	1	1	12783	Structural	Larval type I keratin (Fragment) OS=Rana luteiventris GN=RLKI PE=2 SV=1
tr K9M0N1 K9M0N1_RANCL	5.2	24.44	3	1	1	36407	Structural	Larval-specific keratin 1 (Fragment) OS=Rana clamitans GN=rlk1 PE=2 SV=1
tr C1C4Y0 C1C4Y0_LITCT	5.2	22.88	9	1	1	19605	Enzyme	Mitochondrial inner membrane protease subunit 2 OS=Lithobates catesbeiana GN=IMP2L PE=2 SV=1
tr C1C4G7 C1C4G7_LITCT	5.1	22.71	4	1	1	40431	Regulatory	C10orf27 OS=Lithobates catesbeiana GN=CJ027 PE=2 SV=1
tr C1C521 C1C521_LITCT	9.8	22.21	5	1	1	29713	Enzyme	Exosome complex exonuclease RRP43 OS=Lithobates catesbeiana GN=EXOS8 PE=2 SV=1
tr C1C502 C1C502_LITCT	5.1	22.04	5	1	1	32739	Regulatory	Tropomyosin-1 alpha chain OS=Lithobates catesbeiana GN=TPM1 PE=2 SV=1
sp P13105 TPM1_RANTE	5.1	22.04	5	1	1	32665	Regulatory	Tropomyosin alpha-1 chain OS=Rana temporaria GN=tpm1 PE=2 SV=1
tr G3XF03 G3XF03_9NEOB	10.5	21.51	7	1	1	37529	Enzyme	NADH-ubiquinone oxidoreductase chain 2 OS=Odorrana ishikawae GN=ND2 PE=3 SV=1
sp Q8AYI2 PRGR_RANDY	6.1	21.37	1	1	1	80126	Receptor	Progesterone receptor OS=Rana dybowskii GN=pgr PE=1 SV=1

Brevinin peptides were first identified in the skin secretions of *Rana brevipoda porosa* (reclassified as *Pelophylax porosa*) [33]. Further studies demonstrated that AMPs belonging to the brevinin-1 family are widely distributed in both Eurasian and North American anuran, whereas brevinin-2 peptides have only been found in Eurasian ranids [34]. Currently, brevinin peptides have been found in various amphibian species, including *H. picturata*, *O. hosii*, *H. erythraea*, and *Hylarana spinulosa*. Brevinin-1 and -2 peptides isolated from *H. picturata* and *O. hosii* showed antimicrobial activities against Gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli*) and Gram-positive bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*) [10]. Brevinin-2 peptides from *H. erythraea* inhibits the growth activities of *E. coli* and *S. aureus* and a fungal, *Candida albicans* [11]. Antimicrobial peptides isolated from different anuran species exhibit various effects against different types of microorganisms. For example, brevinin-1 peptide isolated from *Hylarana spinulosa* (Ranidae) inhibits the growth of a variety of Gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus*, *Enterococcus faecium*, *E. faecalis*, and *Nocardia asteroides*), Gram-negative bacteria (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Enterobacteriaceae*, *E. coli*, and *Psychrobacter faecalis*), and fungi (*Candida glabrata* and *C. albicans*) at differing concentrations [7].

The current study's findings notably include the first time that brevinin peptides coming from the foam nests of anuran species have been reported. Almost all peptides that have been extracted, isolated, and documented have come from amphibian skin secretions. In amphibians, these peptides have specific functions including protection from pathogenic microbes, defense from potential predators, wound healing, and oxidant scavenging [27,31,35]. In addition, peptides can also exert multiple functions such as chemotactic and immunomodulating activities, endotoxin neutralization, induction of angiogenesis, and wound repair [36].

4. CONCLUSION

Polypedates leucomystax deposits its eggs in a moist structure called a foam nest. Twenty-two proteins including seven enzymes, six structural proteins, five regulatory proteins, three receptors, and a single AMP (brevinin-2 type) were detected in the foam nests of this species in this study. The importance and functions of these proteins needs to be further investigated. The AMP (brevinin-2 type) is

believed to play a vital role in protecting *P. leucomystax* eggs from pathogenic microorganisms, which also requires further study. The peptide should be isolated and its activities against several bacterial and fungal species tested.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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